

Report

Governance of Citizen Science Networks/Platforms: Shared Experiences

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Abbreviations

BOKU	University of Natural Resources and Life Sciences, Vienna (Austria)
COESO	Collaborative Engagement on Societal Issues project
CS	Citizen Science
CSI	Citizen Science Italy (Italy)
CS-NL	Citizen Science Nederland (Netherlands)
DMP	Data Management Plan
ECSA	European Citizen Science Association (Germany)
EU	European Union
FAIR	Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability, and Reusability
FTE	Full-Time Equivalent
ICTs	Information and Communications Technologies
IPRs	Intellectual Property Rights
JOGL	Just One Giant Lab (France)
LIBER	Association of European Research Libraries (Netherlands)
MOOC	Massive Open Online Course
NGO	Non-Governmental Organisation
ODISSEI	Open Data Infrastructure for Social Science and Economic Innovations (Netherlands)
OPERAS	Open Scholarly Communication in the European Research Areas for Social Sciences and Humanities (Belgium)
RRI	Responsible Research and Innovation
SMART	Specific, Measurable, Achievable, Relevant, and Time-Bound objectives
STEM	Science, Technology, Engineering, and Mathematics
UNESCO	United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization
VA	Vetenskap & Allmänhet (Sweden)
VERA	Virtual Ecosystem for Research Activation

SECTION 1

Citizen science networks and platforms: Key concepts and aims of this report

DÖRLER, D; HEIGL, F

Introduction

Since the early 2010s, several national networks and initiatives have been established to connect different citizen science projects in their respective countries, often across scientific disciplines (Liu et al., 2021). These networks, often with associated online platforms, pursue various goals, such as: (1) displaying citizen science projects to an interested public; (2) connecting citizen science actors to foster innovation and learning; (3) advocating and lobbying for citizen science in their respective contexts; as well as (4) supporting the creation of citizen science project or to improve small “local” projects by facilitating a cooperation with professional researchers. The term citizen science itself and different aspects of its meaning are currently still under much debate (e.g., Heigl et al., 2019; Haklay et al., 2021; Cooper et al., 2021), but for the purpose of this document, we understand citizen science as a research endeavour that non-professional researchers (called citizens in this document) are undertaking alone or (more often) together with professional researchers to reach a research goal, usually but not necessarily among other aims.

Citizen science networks are understood here as formal or informal groups of professional scientists and citizen scientists who want to foster citizen science and work together in diverse aspects of research in or about citizen science. These researchers and/or citizen scientists come from two or more different institutions or can participate as individuals. Network partners can be from one realm of research (e.g., only natural scientists) or several realms of research (e.g., natural scientists, social scientists, and researchers from the humanities).

At the same time, citizen science platforms are interpreted here mainly as websites that display different citizen science projects, and information related to them, to an interested public. These projects can come from one realm of research or several realms of research, or they can display projects from a specific region or country or even from several countries. Typically, they are organised by a citizen science network (but this is not a prerequisite).

Both, networks and platforms, may also offer additional services to project coordinators, citizen scientists or partner institutions.

Background of the working group

In our European Citizen Science Association (ECSA) working group, “Citizen Science Networks”, we combine the knowledge and experience from many networks and platforms that have emerged in the course of the last decade. In the Citizen Science Networks working group, representatives from established and emerging citizen science networks are collaborating to tackle some of these challenges. Experiences for this report were collected mainly from national networks and platforms based in Austria, Belgium, the Czech Republic, Denmark, Italy, the Netherlands, Portugal, and Slovenia. In addition to these national networks and platforms, there are international platforms, such as EU-Citizen.Science and SciStarter which shared their experiences, as well as the Virtual Ecosystem for Research Activation (VERA), which is a platform for citizen science projects from the humanities and social sciences.

Interestingly, the history of these networks and platforms, their development and their institutional

background are very heterogeneous, which provides many different approaches and perspectives to tackle various challenges that are the topic of this report. These include, but are not limited to: funding; organisation of workloads (e.g., organisational structure and IPR); as well as framing of citizen science (e.g., transparent criteria on which projects are listed on online platforms, and which are not) and many more.

Collection of experiences

In a series of online workshops, the working group members shared their experiences in different areas of working for a citizen science network/platform. These areas of experience involve (1) the aims, (2) setup, (3) activities, (4) funding, (5) target groups and communication of citizen science networks and/or platforms, as well as (6) data collected in citizen science networks and/or platforms.

In our workshop series, individual working group members chaired specific areas of experiences and prepared activities to discuss these experiences in each workshop. These activities sometimes involved some pre-workshop work (e.g., filling out a survey) that provided some information on how the member networks and platforms in the working group addressed a specific challenge. During the workshops, the individual chairs offered a structured approach for the members to share their experiences from the different networks (e.g., fishbowls and input presentations) often based on information provided in pre-workshop activities. All experiences were collected in the workshop minutes and together with the information from pre-workshop activities formed the basis for this report.

Aim

This report aims to inform the citizen science community about the challenges or questions faced in developing citizen science networks in different countries. We want to emphasise that there are probably additional challenges that can be very context-specific and that we cannot offer any “how-to” guidelines. However, we think that by sharing the combined experiences from the

member networks and platforms, we can give other people aiming to set up or establish citizen science networks or platforms some information on where to start and what has worked in which contexts.

Furthermore, we would like to emphasise again that since the members of the working group come from relatively few countries, this report may also be seen as a collection of experiences from those countries that may or may not work in other areas of Europe or even the world, where circumstances might be completely different.

Structure of the document

You will find six different sections for the six aforementioned areas of experiences that were discussed in our workshop series (sections 2–7). Each section offers a summary of the workshop and 3–6 bullet points on the main findings of the workshop. Additionally, section 1 gives some insights into the working group’s aim, and section 8 contains the flowchart that provides guidance throughout the document, in case you are only interested in specific areas. The last section highlights the key questions that triggered the discussions in our working group, and that may help you when setting up or coordinating your own citizen science network or platform.

SECTION 2

Aims and goals of networks/platforms

SFORZI, A

Introduction

Citizen science networks can have very different origins, often reflecting a series of interlinked factors, such as the previous existence of citizen science projects in that particular context, the background (including formal or informal role) of promoters, and last but not least, the country's cultural context. There are cases in which the establishment of a network is set from the outset, following a defined work plan. In other cases, the process is more self-regulating, developing a sense of purpose through experience. This quite articulated picture has to be taken into account when describing the aims and goals of a network, because they may change over time, following the progression of the community and its needs, but also in relation to potential opportunities that might arise, such as the availability (or unavailability) of funds, the evolution of the relationships with relevant stakeholders, governmental support, and so on.

Nevertheless, as in many other areas of human activity, effective network planning provides a sound basis for success, particularly when set in the context of adaptive management, where objectives can be defined based on previous actions. Having this in mind, the scope of this section is to build upon the experiences collected from most of the existing citizen science networks in Europe. The aim is to investigate the varied list of options and define those common to a large group of experiences, in order to provide useful insights for those planning to initiate a similar process, as well as for those wishing to adapt their aims by taking inspiration from others' experiences.

Typical aims and goals of citizen science networks and platforms

Prior to the workshop the participants were asked to individually reflect on the aims and goals of their respective networks or platforms. During our workshop on this topic, one of the first questions that arose was: should we focus on "aims" or on "goals"? What are the differences between these two terms? Last but not least, how can differences in the aims and goals of networks, platforms, and communities be beneficial for the international citizen science community? What follows is a brief summary of the discussions we had on this topic.

While the terms "aims" and "goals" are sometimes used interchangeably, particularly in informal contexts, a clear distinction exists, especially when analysing the strategic direction of organisations. In the context of European citizen science networks, "aims" represent the overarching intentions and long-term aspirations that guide their creation and operation. Aims can hence provide a clear illustration of these broader motivations, such as to "increase the democratisation of science, encourage the growth of citizen science and support the public in research processes". In contrast to the broader "aims", the "goals" of European citizen science networks represent more specific, measurable, achievable, relevant, and time-bound (SMART) objectives that these networks set out to accomplish in pursuit of their overarching intentions.

A typical platform goal (both at the European and national level) is, for example, to frame criteria that help networks decide, transparently and impartially, whether a project should be listed as citizen science on online platforms or not. This is a specific and actionable goal with an implied timeframe, and its completion is measurable through the development and adoption of such criteria.

In the case of science library networks, for example, actionable goals might be:

- Build the capacity of libraries to become community hubs for citizen science.
- Support a community of libraries engaging their community in citizen science.
- Broaden the participation of diverse communities in citizen science.
- Shape and accelerate scientific research.

These goals are more targeted than the general aim of promoting citizen science, focusing on specific areas of action and implying measurable progress in terms of increased capacity, broader participation, and accelerated research.

Learning points

Across our experience, several underlying themes emerge as key aims of European citizen science networks. **Building a community of citizen scientists** was, intuitively, the most popular aim, also because it represents a pleonastic response to the need of creating a visible and active entity able to act as a point of reference to advocating for citizen science at the national level. It also includes other related overarching aims, such as engaging civil society, policymakers, and schools in science; promoting citizen science as a valid research method; or laying the foundation for citizens' long-term involvement in projects.

A further common argument that drives the establishment of a citizen science network is the need to **support members and various stakeholders**. That might be realised by displaying an updated catalogue of projects on a platform, hence allowing users to search for information, create opportunities for collaboration, and facilitate the development of new citizen science activities. That might also mean providing a comprehensive set of solutions, ranging from training modules to collecting and sharing citizen science resources, and building up an infrastructure for (open/FAIR) citizen science data. All these goals ultimately provide the ground to reach another overarching aim of a network: to become recognised as the main hub for citizen science in a specific thematic or geographical context.

Some networks were set up to pursue the associated goal of achieving **broader funding opportunities**. As long as an entity is formally established, it can apply for funding, for example, and be eligible for national and/or European grants. Although this may seem like a rather limited “goal”, it has the potential to establish the fundamental conditions necessary for a network to flourish and to secure the resources required for organizing a work plan. In cases where relationships between people or projects are established within an informal, active group, there is strong motivation to formalise the network and provide concrete growth opportunities. Funding is, of course, also crucial for many other aspects of a network. For further reflections on the topic, see the dedicated section 5 of this report.

Other goals include: fostering collaboration and networking among various citizen science actors, promoting public engagement in scientific endeavours and increasing overall scientific literacy within the population, contributing meaningfully to scientific research and effectively addressing pressing societal challenges, influencing policy-making processes and promoting the broader recognition of and integration of citizen science within research and innovation systems, and building the necessary capacity and providing essential resources for citizen science practitioners and participants.

Conclusion

In summary, the aims of a network emphasise its community-building role and, more broadly, the transformative potential of citizen science to contribute to societal progress. The focus on inclusivity and capacity building indicates a long-term commitment to fostering a sustainable and impactful European citizen science movement. By outlining the aim of “engaging the public in support of key mission areas”, the broad strategic intention at a national level is represented. These multifaceted aims reflect the diverse potential of citizen science to contribute to science, society, and policy and are generally aspirational and long-term in their orientation.

On the other hand, goals are focused on tangible outcomes, such as creating a specific platform, developing and delivering training programs, and establishing a defined network of representatives. These are all measurable steps that directly contribute to the broader aim of strengthening the European citizen science community. Across these examples, several recurring themes emerge as goals of European citizen science networks:

- developing and maintaining online platforms and resources to support citizen science projects and connect stakeholders,
- creating and delivering targeted training programs and educational materials for both practitioners and participants,
- establishing and nurturing networks and communities of practice to facilitate collaboration and knowledge sharing,
- conducting research and gathering data to better understand citizen science activities, their impact, and best practices,
- and actively advocating for citizen science within relevant policy and funding contexts to ensure its sustainability and growth.

SECTION 3

Setup of networks and platforms

DUERINCKX, A; GOLD, M; SMANIOTTO, A

Introduction

The structure and setup of a citizen science network or platform can take many forms, influenced by its origins, aims (see section 2), and growth path. Some networks emerge from existing institutions, while others are grassroots initiatives that formalise over time. There is no single “right” way to establish a network—each approach depends on available resources, national contexts, and stakeholder engagement.

This section builds on insights from a dedicated workshop session aimed at understanding how citizen science networks and platforms are set up. The first part explores different organisational models, from informal grassroots initiatives to more formalised structures. The second part examines the role of digital and physical spaces in network coordination, showing how online platforms facilitate outreach and coordination while in-person meetings strengthen engagement and collaboration. By starting from real examples, this section provides a set of experiences to help others navigate the setup and sustainability of their own networks.

Workshop setup: Mapping network structures

To better understand how citizen science networks and platforms are structured, participants completed network cards before the workshop (Figure 1). These cards, hosted on a Miro Board, captured key aspects such as thematic focus, working framework (informal group, legal entity, or linked to an institution), coordination type, meeting spaces, and available resources (funding, human support, or infrastructure). Fifteen networks filled out a network card, representing ten European countries (including two with multiple networks), two European-wide networks, and one international network. In the workshop we then

focused on the working frameworks and meeting spaces as key elements that shape the setup of networks or platforms.

Organisational structures of citizen science networks

The workshop started with a discussion on the organisational structures of the networks represented in the network cards. This discussion revealed the diverse ways citizen science networks are structured and sustained.

Ten out of fifteen networks are **embedded in existing research-oriented organisations** such as natural history museums, governmental agencies, or universities. These networks operate without a separate legal entity. Eight of these ten networks started as bottom-up initiatives, relying on volunteers and informal agreements. Some of them formalised over time in the form of a Memorandum of Understanding or an Association. For example, the Austrian Citizen Science Network started as a grassroots initiative by two PhD students and now functions under a Memorandum of Understanding signed by all its partners. The network has no separate legal entity, but is part of BOKU University in Vienna. Another example is the Danish Citizen Science Network, which started as a bottom-up initiative embedded in Aarhus University and relies on volunteers without official funding or support. The Slovenian CS Network started as a project at the Central Technical Library at the University of Ljubljana, partially funded by the Ministry of Higher Education, Science and Innovation.

A few citizen science networks are **embedded in non-profit organisations** focused on science communication and public engagement. For example, the Belgian CS-platform Iedereen Wetenschapper, is embedded in a science journalism non-profit,

Eos Wetenschap; the Swedish Medborgar Forskning is embedded in Vetenskap & Allmänhet (VA; eng. Public & Science Sweden), a non-profit association focusing on citizen science, responsible research and innovation (RRI), and science communication; and the Belgian Scivil is embedded in a non-profit organisation focusing on science outreach and education in the science, technology, engineering, and mathematics (STEM) fields.

Another group of networks is **embedded in European infrastructures or European-funded projects**. For example, VERA, an online platform focused on citizen science in Social Sciences and Humanities, was created within the European Collaborative Engagement on Societal Issues (COESO) project and is embedded in the research infrastructure of the Open Scholarly Communication in the European Research Areas for Social Sciences and Humanities (OPERAS). Also, the EU-Citizen.Science platform was developed within a European-funded project and embedded in the European Citizen Science Association (ECSA).

Finally, some networks evolve over time into **separate non-profit organisations** with their own legal entity. For example, ECSA and CS Italia emerged from an informal network of researchers and communicators interested in citizen science in Europe and Italy and formalised into non-profit associations. Another example is the Portuguese CS network, which started as a bottom-up initiative, grew from biennial national CS meetings, and was promoted by the Secretary of State for Science, Technology and Higher Education. The movement grew from an informal initiative of interested people until it was formalised as a non-profit association, without official funding but relying on membership fees.

A common challenge among networks is securing funding for coordination efforts. Many networks currently function without formal funding, making long-term sustainability a pressing concern (see also the section 5).

Figure 1. Network card template.
Source: Own elaboration.

Digital and physical meeting spaces of citizen science networks

Networks often start through the initiative of a few inspired individuals and the will to collaborate around a shared goal, bringing together like-minded people to exchange knowledge, resources, and expertise. To grow a network, it needs **dedicated spaces**—physical, digital, or both—where members can connect, share ideas, and coordinate activities. While physical spaces foster deeper engagement and relationship-building, digital platforms enhance accessibility and allow for broader outreach. A platform, whether digital or physical, can serve as a tool to support the network, but the foundation always remains the people and their shared purpose.

The second part of the workshop discussed how digital and physical spaces complement each other in achieving network objectives, emphasizing the importance of choosing the right space for specific activities.

Digital meeting spaces

Many networks rely heavily on digital spaces for coordination and engagement. Common digital tools and spaces include:

- Websites: Either as standalone platforms or embedded within the host organisation's website. Some networks also maintain dedicated citizen science platforms to showcase citizen science projects.
- Social media and newsletters: Used to share updates, success stories, and opportunities for involvement (see section 6).
- Blogs and podcasts: Providing deeper engagement through expert insights, interviews, and discussions (see section 6).
- Online meetings, training sessions, and workshops: Regular online meetings help networks remain active, especially when in-person gatherings are not feasible (see section 4).

While some networks invest in dedicated digital platforms for project collaboration and visibility, others operate without them and use more straightforward online communication tools. For

example, VERA is a collaborative digital space where researchers can explore and manage projects, connect with others, and use integrated tools to communicate, co-create, and secure funding for impactful initiatives within the domain of social sciences and humanities. Scivil, on the other hand—the citizen science center in Belgium—relies on more straightforward tools such as an informative website, a newsletter, social media channels, blogs, and online workshops to engage its community and share knowledge.

Physical meeting spaces

Although many networks operate primarily online, physical meetings remain valuable for building relationships and strengthening collaboration. However, the frequency of in-person meetings varies:

- Some networks, such as Österreich forscht in Austria or Ciência Cidadã in Portugal, hold annual or biennial meetings to bring all network members together.
- Networks with formal structures such as SciStarter, Scivil in Belgium and OeAD-Center for Citizen Science in Austria, tend to have more regular online or physical gatherings.
- Public libraries and other neutral spaces can serve as valuable meeting locations, especially for networks without institutional affiliations. For example the Slovenian CS Network started as a project at the Central Technical Library at the University of Ljubljana. Libraries offer inclusive environments that welcome both researchers and the general public in neutral, welcoming spaces.

Balancing digital and physical spaces to achieve network goals

While digital spaces enable accessibility, physical spaces foster deeper engagement. A well-structured network benefits from combining digital and physical meeting spaces, choosing the right space based on the network objectives and the specific activity (Table 1).

Table 1:
The roles of physical and digital spaces for the three main goals (see also section 2) of citizen science networks

Network goal	Physical spaces	Digital spaces
Public outreach	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Engage hard-to-reach groups that are unfamiliar with online platforms. – Extend digital presence, which is essential for deeper engagement. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Reach a broad audience. – Share information widely.
Promoting citizen science	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Facilitate presentations, exhibitions and interactive discussions. – Enhance credibility through in-person debates that foster deeper understanding. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Provide information via websites, online platforms and mailing lists.
Networking	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Strengthen community identity. – Foster deeper connections. – Encourage organic collaboration. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Enable broad initial connections and ongoing communication.

Conclusion

Citizen science networks take diverse forms, from networks with separate legal entities to networks embedded in research or non-profit organisations to informal grassroots efforts. Most networks start through bottom-up initiatives, often relying on volunteers and informal agreements.

As these networks grow, they must also **establish spaces**—both digital and physical—to coordinate activities, engage their community, and foster collaboration. Both digital and physical spaces are essential. Digital platforms support broad outreach and facilitate coordination, while in-person meetings strengthen deeper collaboration and engagement. Balancing these spaces strategically enhances a network’s impact. There is no single formula for success—sharing experiences helps networks refine their approaches and grow sustainably.

SECTION 4

Activities and working groups

SPELT, A; TIAGO, P

Introduction

One of the important parts of being a network is providing the opportunity for the members to come together, meet new people, and exchange knowledge, thus actually networking. This can happen through a wide variety of activities, from in-person workshops and networking days to online webinars and public engagement activities. Organising activities is also a great way to keep the members of the network engaged with the network itself. A more in-depth way for members to engage with each other is by creating working groups in a network. These working groups can be created on a wide variety of topics and themes, but with the general aim of bringing people interested in one topic together to, for example, exchange ideas, good practices, and challenges. Although organising activities seems to be the best way to bring members together to exchange and learn from each other, the possibility and the number of activities that a network can organise vary a lot and depend on other factors discussed in this report (e.g., aims, funding, and target groups). The scope of this section is to provide an overview of the current activities organised by the existing citizen science networks in Europe and to share their experiences, good practices, challenges, and opportunities for those who are planning to start organising such activities themselves.

The activities and working groups of a citizen science network: A survey overview

The working group members filled out a survey on activities and working groups before the workshop. The survey had two parts: general activities and working groups. For general activities, questions related to type, frequency, geographical spread, representation, funding, and challenges. For working groups, questions focused on type, topics, representation, frequency, language, support, environment, and challenges.

The survey included responses from 17 networks, of which 12 were from European countries, one was Europe-wide, and one was based in South Africa (Figure 2). Not all networks organised activities and working groups; 4 networks did not manage any activity, 8 networks organised both, 4 networks organised only activities, and 1 network organised only working groups.

For the networks that organised activities, networking meetings were the most commonly held (92%), followed by conferences (67%), workshops (58%), and webinars (42%). The other aspects of activities (e.g., frequency, geographical spread, and funding for the activities) varied both across the different types of activities as well as within one type of activity. For example, the frequency of network meetings varied from monthly to biannually, from local to European, and both in-person and online.

For networks that organised working groups, 67% named them working groups, whereas 33% named them thematic groups. One network had a community of practice. The main topics of the working groups were communication, biodiversity, education, platform, universities, data, citizen science status, and health. The representation within working groups was comprehensive, ranging from academics, data professionals, and other researchers to citizens, journalists, NGOs, policymakers, field experts, funding organisations, and teachers. Similar to the activities, the frequency with which the working groups met varied from bi-weekly to once a year. The online environments used for collaboration were Google Docs/Drive, Miro, Teams, Zoom, and JOGL. Several networks provided support for the working groups in terms of coordination, funding, and feedback.

Figure 2. Activities and working groups of the Citizen Science networks that responded to the survey (created with mapchart.net).

Learning points: Challenges and recommendations

The following challenges and recommendations are based on the survey responses and workshop discussions. While this is not an extensive list of challenges and recommendations for organising activities, these insights reflect the experiences of the participating networks.

Activities challenge: Lack of (coordination) time and funding

Most citizen science networks are coordinated by scientific staff employed at specific institutions. However, employers do not always see the coordination of a citizen science network as part of the job description. Therefore, the coordination of the network and the activities needs to be done in spare time. Besides time, funding is one of

the biggest challenges for organising activities, especially for newly emerged or emerging networks. Most networks fund their activities via third-party projects, but they struggle to make this approach sustainable. If no project proposal gets funded, then the activities are also over.

Recommendations:

- Make a list of activities you would like to **organise and prioritise** them together with the community. Ask them which ones they definitely would prefer to see happen and organise accordingly.
- Setting up a specific **association with several stakeholders** (e.g., the Italian Network) or a **knowledge centre within an organisation** (e.g., Scivil) can help create more time and activities (although this depends on funding).

- **Integrating network activities** into already existing (outreach) events (e.g., European Researchers' Night, science festivals, and science fairs) to save time and possibly secure funding.

Activities challenge: Engaging (hard-to-reach) people in activities

During organized activities, it is usually the same group of people who are active and engaged. This can be very beneficial to your active group of members. However, it is also important to include other groups of people. For example, not all networks can reach or include citizen scientists, for example, because of challenges related to inclusive activities, such as online meetings where people might not have Wi-Fi (e.g., the South African Network). Reaching these people requires significant resources, which most networks generally lack.

Recommendations:

- **Adjust the timing of activities** to the groups you want to reach out to (e.g., schedule events not on workdays during the day for citizen scientists, but rather during lunchtime, in the evening, or on weekends).
- **Actively involve stakeholders** from your target groups in organising activities that can help attract others from these groups.
- **Create a targeted communication strategy** and outreach method to attract a specific group because not all groups use the same communication channel.
- **Integrating your activities** in other activities (e.g., non-scientific events) can also help attract new people (e.g., a citizen science marketplace at a farmers market).

Working groups challenge: Supporting working groups from the network

Working groups are (mostly) voluntarily led by one of the working group members. However, sometimes there is coordination and support from the network, but this is very diverse across the networks (e.g., ECSA and Citizen Science Nederland have a small funding pot available for each working group). The funding and coordination time also limit how much support can be given from the network to the working groups.

Recommendations:

- Find out **what kind of working groups** are needed. The citizen science community should be involved first before setting up working groups, so there will not be too many working groups to support.
- If possible, set up a small fund to **support the working groups' activities**, such as catering or meeting room costs.
- Set up **specific guidelines for the working groups**, including a structured framework and use of network infrastructures (e.g., network website, social media, and newsletter).
- **Facilitate a (quarterly) meeting** with all working group chairs to connect with each other, give updates, and exchange experiences.

Working groups challenge: Keeping the working groups active

When working groups are created, it is a challenge to keep more than one working group 'alive' at a time, as it requires significant effort. Think of keeping the participants involved and proactive, making it efficient and worthwhile for participants. Besides, it is quite challenging to assess the activity level of the working groups. In particular, when a central person (e.g., the speaker) leaves a working group, the working group's activity seems to decrease, and it is difficult to increase the activity level again without stepping in as a speaker yourself.

Recommendations:

- At least **two people should be responsible** for one working group so that they are engaged in coordinating and leading it.
- **Develop a common goal** and corresponding tasks to keep participants motivated to invest their free time.
- Make sure there is an **active communication contact** and a shared environment where people can meet and discuss.
- **Provide a place** (e.g., network meeting) where working group members can physically meet at least once a year.
- Keep engagement high and relevant by **meeting frequently**, depending also on the goal and tasks described.

SECTION 5

Funding of networks and platforms

DUERINCKX A; SMANIOTTO, A; LUIS, C

Introduction

Securing funding is one of the main challenges faced by most citizen science networks and platforms. Still, there is no one-size-fits-all approach to securing funding. Success in obtaining funding is often deeply contextual, shaped by factors such as the local political and funding landscape, institutional structures, funding information availability, and the specific aims of a network or platform (see section 2). What proves effective for one network may not work for another, even within similar contexts. This section presents a range of stories from various networks and platforms to illustrate the diversity of approaches, challenges, and opportunities in securing funding. By highlighting these experiences, we aim to offer insights into the complexities of funding citizen science initiatives, helping others identify potential strategies that might resonate with their unique circumstances.

How are citizen science networks funded?

In preparation for the session, a survey was sent out to all working group members. It included two tracks. In the first track, for fully or partially funded networks, questions focused on funding sources, supported activities, and actions that led to securing funding. In the second track, for non-funded networks, questions focused on funding attempts and challenges. All respondents also reported how many people run their network.

The survey received responses from 14 networks in 11 European countries, along with SciStarter as an international participant. Nine networks had at least partial funding, mainly from national governments (44%) or a mix of public and private sources (22%), while six had no dedicated funding. Other funding sources included membership fees, European projects, and universities. Many networks

started with temporary public funding, with some transitioning to stable institutional support, while others remain on repeatable and shorter-term funding (typically 3–5 years). Some also secure private funding for specific tasks or supplement income with membership fees.

Funded networks primarily spend on personnel, meetings, events, infrastructure based on the information and communications technologies (ICTs), and promotional materials, with less funding for working groups, content creation, and running projects. Both funded and non-funded networks are usually run by 1–4 people. In non-funded networks, work is unpaid or covered through other roles, while funded networks allocate 1–2.2 full-time equivalent (FTE) positions for running and coordinating the network. Partially funded networks often face financial constraints, with only a small portion of time compensated.

Learning points: General recommendations for securing funding

The following recommendations for securing funding are based on survey responses and workshop discussions. While there is no universal solution for securing funding, these insights reflect what has worked (or not worked) for various networks and highlight the main challenges.

A. Create visibility for citizen science and share success stories

Securing funding for citizen science starts with **making its value visible**. If decision-makers are unaware of citizen science, they are unlikely to support it financially. Networks should highlight success stories and showcase impactful initiatives. Clearly demonstrate both the need for citizen science and its potential societal and scientific benefits.

B. Create a network of partners

Effective lobbying is not a solo effort—creating a strong **coalition of partners** strengthens the message. Collaborating with institutions, researchers, and other stakeholders interested in citizen science can amplify advocacy efforts and help to identify what kind of funding is the most appropriate. Engaging with the right people, whether they hold formal influence or simply share a passion for citizen science, can help push the agenda forward.

C. Demonstrate impact

Additionally, **demonstrating impact with concrete evidence** is essential. Providing data on successful citizen science initiatives—both locally and internationally—adds credibility, making the case more compelling. Transparency and a science-based approach strengthen trust among potential funders and policymakers.

D. Leverage existing policy papers

Leveraging existing policy papers mentioning citizen science, such as the United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization (UNESCO) “Recommendation on Open Science” (2021), national citizen science strategies, and reports on the national or international state of citizen science, can provide a robust foundation for advocacy. These documents help align citizen science with broader policy goals and reinforce its importance within national and international research agendas.

E. Leverage the European dimension

Success stories from other countries can demonstrate the impact of citizen science networks, policies, and funding models. These examples and European-level initiatives can inspire national strategies. Positioning your network within a broader European context and highlighting successful examples from other countries enhances credibility and can increase the likelihood of securing funding.

Overview of funding models for citizen science networks

Citizen science networks rely on a variety of funding sources, each with its own advantages and limitations (Table 2). Many networks secure partial or temporary funding, ranging from a few months to a few years. Some only receive funding for specific citizen science events or projects, or funding only for direct costs but not personnel.

Funding can be obtained through grant writing and applying to open funding calls, by directly engaging with possible funders such as national or regional governments, or the network’s host organisation, such as universities and other research institutions, or by establishing a membership organisation. Across all funding models, one of the biggest challenges that networks face is securing long-term financial support, highlighting the need for diverse and flexible funding strategies.

Table 2. Advantages and disadvantages of funding models for citizen science networks

Advantages	Disadvantages
Governmental/institutional funding	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Provides long-term stability and recognition. - Strengthens the position of citizen science within national or institutional strategies. - It can cover core operational costs and reduce reliance on short-term grants. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Highly dependent on political priorities and policy changes. - It often requires long-term advocacy and negotiation. - Processes can be slow and bureaucratic.
Applying for grants	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Can provide substantive funding for specific projects, operational costs, and/or personnel costs. - It helps build credibility and demonstrate impact. - Can enable growth and innovation within the network. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Highly competitive and often time-consuming. - Requires specialised knowledge that limits getting this type of funding to those who have this specialised knowledge (mainly researchers, not citizens). - Funding is typically temporary, requiring ongoing efforts to secure new grants. - Administrative burden to manage projects. - Limited availability of grant calls that align with setting up/sustaining citizen science networks and platforms.
Membership association	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Provides a formal structure for the network, making it easier to engage with potential funders. - Clearly defines who is part of the network and demonstrates active support for citizen science. - Examples such as ECSA and Citizen Science Italia show that this model can be effective. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Membership fees often generate limited income and are insufficient to support broader activities. - Managing memberships can create a significant administrative burden. - Fees may exclude smaller, grassroots projects or initiatives with limited budgets. A tiered membership model can help address this. - Paying members may expect specific services, shifting the network's focus from collaboration to service provision. Clear communication about how fees are used can mitigate this risk.

Inspiring stories from across Europe

Citizen Science Network Austria: From voluntary to fully funded

In 2014, two PhD students created the *Österreich forscht* platform in their free time, without external funding. By 2017, it received partial funding from the university and the Ministry of Science and Research and the Citizen Science Network Austria was formally established through a Memorandum of Understanding. By 2019, the network had become fully funded through BOKU University, though third-party funding was still needed for events and projects. A key factor in this success was the university's change in rectorate in 2018, which supported citizen science.

Citizen Science Italy: From informal network to membership organisation

Citizen Science Italy (CSI) started informally, with initial funding for a citizen science conference from universities and the Ministry of Environment. Early activities focused on projects. In 2021, additional funding from the EU-Citizen.Science project and the Museum of Natural History Maremma allowed for the organisation of a second national conference, sparking the idea to formalise the network. After a year of discussions, CSI was established in February 2023 as a membership organisation, with fees providing limited income for the association, while offering a formal platform for dialogue with institutional stakeholders such as the Ministry of Science, Research, and Innovation.

Citizen Science networks in Belgium: Two complementary organisations

In Flanders, Belgium, two complementary citizen science organisations exist. The online platform Iedereen Wetenschapper, launched in 2015 by the science journalism organisation Eos Wetenschap, connects the public to citizen science projects and benefits from synergies with Eos's other science journalism activities. The network Scivil was founded in 2019 through a five-year funding agreement with the Flemish Government, inspired by the Austrian CS policy initiatives. Scivil supports CS project initiators through capacity building and networking activities. In 2024, its funding agree-

ment was renewed for another five years. Both organisations collaborate closely to advance citizen science in Belgium.

Citizen Science Network Slovenia: The library as a starting point

In Slovenia, citizen science emerged through LIBER's activities at the Central Technical Library at the University of Ljubljana. After joining ECSA, the library secured funding from the Ministry of Higher Education, Science and Innovation's "Action Plan for Open Science", which included citizen science. The library launched the Slovenian Citizen Science Network, the website <https://citizenscience.si>, and partnered with other institutions. In November 2023, Slovenia held its first national Citizen Science Conference, and the network has a coordinator from a public library and has several active working groups. The platform offers news, a catalogue of projects, a calendar of events and presentations, a list of available infrastructure and other resources for citizen science initiatives.

Citizen Science Nederland: Embedded in the National Open Science Strategy

In the Netherlands, the Citizen Science Nederland (CS-NL) network developed under the National Programme Open Science, which received funding from the Ministry of Science, Education, and Culture in 2021–2022, also providing limited initial funding for CS-NL for establishing online communication channels and organising the first national Citizen Science network day. In 2023, the network was sustained by European project funding, enabling it to maintain communication efforts. Finally, in 2024, the Ministry allocated significant investment in Open Science, including four years of funding for CS-NL, though securing long-term funding remains challenging.

Conclusion

Securing funding requires a mix of visibility, advocacy, persistence, and sometimes luck—being in the right place at the right time, meeting the right people, or benefiting from policy shifts. However, persistence is key; continuing to apply and adapt increases the chances of success. Building a strong network and consistently demonstrating citizen science's value helps create future funding opportunities.

SECTION 6

Target groups and communication

TOMASSON, L; TIAGO, P; LUIS, C

Introduction

Citizen science networks serve diverse societal groups, with target audiences varying across national and transnational platforms. These networks foster collaboration among researchers, NGOs, public and private institutions, and civil society, contributing significantly to research, education, policy-making, decision-making, and community engagement.

Effective communication is essential for sustaining and expanding these networks. Internal communication ensures coherence within the network, while external strategies amplify visibility and outreach, as well as increase and sustain participation. Choosing the proper communication channels, adapting strategies to target audiences, and addressing resource limitations are critical for the success of citizen science implementation.

Methods and data collection

This analysis draws from survey responses by representatives of eight citizen science networks across Europe, including six national and two transnational platforms and networks (ECSA and VERA). The survey explored key aspects such as target groups, membership policies, and communication strategies.

Insights and recommendations

Target groups and membership policies

Citizen science networks primarily target researchers, with all eight networks emphasising this group as a central focus. NGOs also emerge as a significant audience, actively engaged by seven of the surveyed networks. However, several networks demonstrate unique approaches to membership and collaboration, reflecting their specific priorities and contexts.

- In **Portugal**, the network actively incorporates librarians into its framework, recognising their potential to foster collaboration and facilitate access to resources and knowledge. This inclusion broadens the scope of the network's outreach and strengthens its ties within the community.
- **Austria** takes a more formal approach by restricting membership exclusively to institutions. This model ensures that all members commit to the network's objectives through a signed memorandum of understanding, establishing a strong foundation for accountability and alignment with institutional goals.
- **Italy** adopts a highly inclusive strategy by functioning as an open association that welcomes individuals, institutions, and projects. Flexible membership fees cater to different member capacities, resulting in a predominance of individual members. This inclusive structure not only promotes widespread participation but also enables the network to pursue funding opportunities and partnerships more effectively.
- In the **Netherlands**, the network operates without a structured membership system but achieves balanced participation of scientists and citizens. This approach reflects a commitment to equality and openness, allowing for organic growth and diverse contributions. However, the absence of membership fees underscores the challenges of securing sustainable funding.

These varying approaches illustrate the diversity in how citizen science networks operate. Striking a balance between inclusivity and organisational needs is vital for ensuring long-term sustainability and fulfilling the network's mission.

Learning points: Communication strategies

Internal communication

Internal communication (i.e., communication within the network) is the pillar of any network, fostering collaboration, transparency, and inclusivity among members. Networks should prioritise tools and methods that resonate with their members' preferences. Personalised communication is especially impactful, but flexibility and adaptability remain key to maintaining effective communication channels supporting collaboration and shared goals. Internal communication supports members' retention and active engagement, particularly citizen scientists, by ensuring they feel informed, included, and valued. It facilitates coordination, nurtures a sense of community, and helps maintain motivation through regular updates and shared goals. Transparency and inclusivity should guide the design of communication channels, ensuring that all members feel represented and informed.

Email remains the primary channel for most networks, valued for its accessibility, reliability, ease of use, and ability to reach a broad audience effectively. Austria exemplifies the potential of personalised emails to foster stronger connections within the network. By addressing recipients directly and shaping messages to their specific needs or interests, the network enhances the relevance and impact of its communication. On the other hand, Portugal emphasises the value of concise, well-targeted newsletters. Recognising that lengthy or overly detailed updates may deter readership, the network focuses on delivering clear and succinct messages that capture attention and prompt engagement.

However, many networks supplement email communication with other communication channels and tools to enhance engagement and foster a sense of community. Platforms such as **Slack**, **WhatsApp**, and **newsletters** are the most used supplementary tools for engagement. Slack and WhatsApp are frequently used as collaborative tools, particularly for real-time discussions and quick exchanges among members. Newsletters also play a vital role, offering a structured and

visually appealing way to share updates, announcements, and opportunities. These newsletters are often shaped to suit the preferences of the network's members.

External communication

Effective external communication (i.e., communication with people who are not part of the network) requires consistent effort and innovative approaches. Establishing dedicated roles for communication professionals ensures that outreach efforts remain organised and impactful.

Collaboration with media professionals and influencers can broaden outreach significantly. Journalists, bloggers, and social media influencers bring unique expertise and networks that amplify the reach of citizen science initiatives. Partnerships with marketing agencies or digital creators can enhance the appeal and accessibility of communication materials.

Social media platforms, including **Twitter/X**, **Bluesky**, **Facebook**, **Instagram**, **Threads**, **Mastodon** and **LinkedIn**, serve as key channels for engaging with broader audiences. These channels, along with blogs, websites, and public events, provide a dynamic mix of outreach opportunities, allowing networks to share updates, promote events, and highlight achievements. Using these tools effectively helps increase visibility and reach diverse groups.

Approximately half of the surveyed networks employ dedicated communication personnel to manage these activities. However, limited resources often pose significant challenges, constraining the ability to maintain consistent and impactful communication efforts. This limitation underscores the importance of strategic resource allocation and creative solutions to optimise outreach.

Austria provides a notable example of tailored communication strategies through its journalist mailing list. The network has enhanced its ability to distribute press releases and secure media coverage by **curating a list of media professionals**

interested in citizen science. This targeted approach ensures that news reaches the right audience, increasing the likelihood of impactful dissemination. Austria's experience highlights the value of building and maintaining strong relationships with journalists as a basis for effective external communication.

Other networks also emphasise collaboration with media professionals. Italy benefits from the involvement of a retired journalist who curates news for press releases, ensuring accuracy and relevance. Similarly, Portugal plans to engage journalists through press releases, aiming to establish a robust media presence and foster long-term partnerships.

External communication serves multiple goals: it enhances visibility, supports the recruitment of new participants, and strengthens the societal and political relevance of citizen science. It plays a key role in raising awareness, influencing decision-makers, and demonstrating the value of ongoing and completed initiatives to the wider public.

Focus on key stakeholders

To build sustainable relationships with crucial audiences, citizen science networks should create detailed blueprints for engagement and communication plans. These can guide interactions with funders, policymakers, and citizen scientists, aligning communication efforts with their specific needs and expectations. Involving citizen scientists in working groups fosters a sense of ownership and ensures that communication strategies are both inclusive and effective.

Partnering with marketing agencies or digital creators can amplify the network's messages, making them more appealing to a broader audience. Additionally, fostering collaborations with funders and policymakers can help secure support for long-term initiatives (see section 5). At the same time, targeted outreach to citizen scientists ensures their active participation and contribution to the network's mission.

Conclusion

The experiences presented here underscore the critical importance of strategic, inclusive, and adaptable communication approaches. Internally, the emphasis on accessible tools, personalised communication, and concise messaging ensures that members remain engaged, informed, and connected. By using tools that engage with their audiences and adopting strategies that prioritise transparency and inclusivity, networks can strengthen internal cohesion and foster a collaborative environment.

Externally, using social media, blogs, websites, and public outreach events expands the reach of citizen science initiatives, creating opportunities for broader engagement. Integrating dedicated communication roles and strategic media partnerships enhances visibility and ensures that key messages reach the target audiences. Approaches such as journalist mailing lists and collaboration with influencers or digital creators further amplify the impact.

The experiences from our citizen science networks showed that they align their communication strategies with their audiences' priorities. Engaging groups through targeted blueprints, working groups, and collaborative initiatives fosters stronger relationships and ensures that communication efforts are both relevant and effective.

Moving forward, citizen science networks should continue to innovate and adapt, finding creative ways to overcome resource constraints and extend their reach. By building on their strengths, addressing challenges proactively, and maintaining a commitment to inclusivity and collaboration, these networks can amplify their contributions to science and society. A sustained focus on effective communication will not only strengthen their internal structures but also empower them to engage with the world in meaningful and impactful ways.

SECTION 7

Data services

TROJAN, J

Introduction

Establishing and operating citizen science networks and platforms involves addressing critical needs related to data services. This section explores the findings of a study conducted by the European Citizen Science Association (ECSA) Working Group Citizen Science Networks, focusing on the current state of data services provided by such platforms and the gaps that need to be addressed.

Mapping current data services

The study aimed to map state-of-the-art approaches in data services offered by citizen science platforms and networks. The survey (conducted in January 2024) involved 12 respondents representing various national and regional citizen science platforms and networks, including Österreich forscht (Austria), Citizen Science Italia, Portuguese Citizen Science Network, CitizenScience.cz (Czech Republic), Iedereen Wetenschapper (Belgium), CitizenScience.si (Slovenia), Citizen Science Nederland and Medborgarforskning.se (Sweden), including representatives of ECSA. These platforms play a pivotal role in supporting citizen science projects by offering essential services for data management, metadata hosting, website hosting, data collection, and training. The research employed a mixed-methods approach, combining a structured questionnaire and expert discussions.

The questionnaire focused on existing data services and in potential data service gaps:

- Existing data services:
 - Data management plans (DMPs), metadata hosting, project website hosting, data collection hosting, and training programmes.
 - Platforms such as EU-Citizen.Science and Zooniverse were frequently cited as benchmarks for offering data services.

- Identified data service gaps:
 - Participants highlighted the importance of services such as metadata hosting and training, while pointing out underdeveloped areas such as DMP support.

The outcomes of the survey were then discussed during a working group meeting, which emphasised regional challenges, including language barriers, infrastructure limitations, and disciplinary-specific needs.

Existing data services

The results revealed significant variability in the services provided. Approximately 30% of platforms are not offering any data-related services. Among those that do, the most common offerings include training—either regular or ad-hoc—and metadata services. Metadata services usually just let users add project-related information. However, support for comprehensive data management plans is notably scarce. Platforms such as EU-Citizen.Science and global initiatives such as SciStarter for example, have gained popularity within the community due to their robust offerings, such as various resources and training solutions, including massive open online courses (MOOCs).

Identifying gaps in data services

The survey also highlighted the community's unmet needs. Training emerged as the most critical requirement, particularly in areas related to data management plans and the various stages of handling data effectively. Respondents emphasised the importance of equipping citizen scientists with skills to manage data responsibly and efficiently throughout their projects.

Most participants identified metadata services as essential, underscoring their role in ensuring

that project information is well-organised and accessible. Conversely, hosting services for data collections were deemed less critical compared to other needs. Again, platforms such as EU-Citizen.Science and Zooniverse were frequently cited as exemplary models for providing comprehensive data services (e.g., data visualisation or customisation of the project page).

Learning points:

Best practices and recommendations

Based on these findings, several best practices can be recommended for setting up and organising citizen science networks:

1. **Prioritise training programmes:** Platforms should invest in regular training sessions focused on data management plans, metadata handling, and general data literacy. These programmes can empower participants to navigate complex data-related challenges effectively. Example: Austria's cross-border webinar model demonstrates the value of collaborative learning.
2. **Enhance metadata services:** Simplified, yet robust metadata tools should be developed to enable users to document their projects' completeness, consistency, and comprehensiveness. This service is crucial for fostering collaboration and ensuring long-term accessibility of project information. In addition, adherence to FAIR principles is key to data management.
3. **Adopt proven models:** Platforms can draw inspiration from successful initiatives, for example, EU-Citizen.Science, Zooniverse or SciStarter, which offer user-friendly interfaces and comprehensive support for various aspects of citizen science projects. Platforms such as ODISSEI (Netherlands) and EU-Citizen.Science provides scalable frameworks for metadata and project hosting.
4. **Use multilingual resources:** Translate training materials to cater to non-English-speaking participants, as is done in the Czech Republic.
5. **Promote collaboration:** National and regional networks should collaborate with established international platforms to share resources, expertise, and best practices. Such partnerships can help bridge service gaps while fostering innovation.

Conclusion

Citizen science networks play a vital role in enabling public participation in scientific research by providing essential infrastructure and support. However, as this study demonstrates, there is a pressing need to address gaps in data services—particularly in training and metadata management—to enhance the effectiveness of these platforms. By adopting best practices and leveraging successful models, citizen science networks can better serve their communities while advancing scientific discovery.

SECTION 8

Flowchart

DÖRLER, D;
HEIGL, F;
TROJAN, J

SECTION 9

Instead of ending: Key questions for continuous development

DÖRLER, D; HEIGL, F; SFORZI, A

The collection of the different experiences of all the networks that shared their story in our working group shows a wide degree of variability in all the aspects we analysed. The first lesson learned is that there is no “one-size-fits-all” solution for setting up or organising a citizen science platform or network. However, it should be tackled by taking into account the specific context, as well as taking advantage of the experiences gathered by other networks in similar circumstances. The coordinators’ decisions in the different networks and platforms made concerning aims, goals, methods, or processes were—as a matter of fact—shaped by circumstances and different cultures. What worked in one setting might not work at all in another setting. Therefore, we would like to emphasise that the findings in this document are not supposed to be a recipe for setting up or coordinating a network, primarily since the working group consists mainly of European representatives. Nevertheless, the experience we have gained in our working group allows us to derive questions that can be asked when setting up a platform or network, the answers to which will help us to understand which paths are more effective.

One of the first questions you might ask is, **what are the aims and goals of my network or platform?** As we have seen in section 2, answers can be very different and span from more ideological aims (e.g., to raise awareness for citizen science) to very practical goals (e.g., to be able to get funding). Often, a collection of aims and goals drives the foundation of a network or a platform. Answering this first question is crucial since many other decisions depend on it.

How you set up a network or platform, meaning how you organise and coordinate yourself, will be another important question. This will probably

depend on any pre-existing structures or institutions you might have access to and what you want to achieve. Section 3 highlighted some interesting experiences that can inspire your journey.

Activities in different formats can make your platform or network thrive since they enable new people to enter your network or platform and share their knowledge, or they can make citizens aware of the possibility of participating in research projects. Therefore, you need to think about **which kinds of activities you want to organise and if working groups are a part of these activities**. Section 4 shows many examples of activities that cover everything from small online webinars to big national conferences, and it also explains the challenges and opportunities of establishing working groups.

All the above-mentioned aspects need more or less funding to be realised, so sooner rather than later, the question of **how such a network or platform can be funded** will arise. Section 5 shared different stories of getting funding from various sources for such endeavours, and very often, mixed funding has been an effective path. However, different funding sources bring different opportunities and disadvantages, and they need to be aligned with the aims of your network or platform.

Depending on the funding, the aims, and the activities you plan for your network or platform, you also need to think about your **target groups and your communication channels**. Today, a multitude of communication channels exist, but it takes much time to communicate through several of these channels in parallel. Therefore, it is important to have a clear understanding of whom you want to involve and for what, to make a decision about the right channels for your network or

platform. Section 6 shares some insights on the decisions made by some of the networks and platforms present in our working group.

When you run a network or a platform, you always collect some kind of data. **What kind of data and for what purposes you store the data** is another question you might want to ask yourself. Section 7 gives you some clues on what other networks and platforms have done and what might suit you.

In conclusion, our report provides an articulated set of clues and solutions rather than one-size-fits-all recommendations for setting up and coordinating a citizen science network or platform. Nevertheless, answering the questions formulated through the text and taking advantage of what others have already experienced might be a great starting point in advancing the democratisation of science.

Making existing citizen science projects and resources visible and accessible, for example, through a platform or network, allows citizens to engage in the activities that suit them most, allowing them to play an active role in society.

Regardless of the way a network has been established, showcasing practices and engaging the public in data collection and training programmes at the national level can have relevant impacts in terms of the availability of scientific data to potentially inform, for example, management measures and policy. These are among the main reasons that withstand the creation of a network.

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Appendix:

Network/platform profiles

Österreich forscht
www.citizen-science.at

Network/platform name: Österreich forscht

Country: Austria

Website: <https://www.citizen-science.at/en/>

Coordination by: BOKU University

Contact person: Florian Heigl & Daniel Dörler

E-Mail: office@citizen-science.at

Active since: 2014

Aims:

- Networking: connecting project coordinators, citizens and practitioners
- Development of citizen science: in working groups, at workshops etc.
- Quality control: quality criteria for citizen science projects on Österreich forscht
- Public outreach: dedicated events (e.g. annual Austrian Citizen Science Conference has a public day) or (co)organizing other events (e.g. European Researchers' Night), social media, podcast and blog.

Setup:

- founded by two PhD students in their free time without official mandate or funding in 2014
- CSNA based on a Memorandum of Understanding, but is not a legal entity per se

Activities:

- Annual general meetings (2x/year), conferences (1x/year), public outreach activities (15-20x/year), webinars (10-12x/year), workshops (6-8x/year)
- national and local outreach (depending on the activity)
- both hybrid and in person (depending on the activity)
- for project coordinators, citizens, researchers, funders (depending on the activity)

- funded through platform budget, third-party funding, fees (depending on the activity)
- aims are networking, development of citizen science, public outreach (depending on the activity)
- several working groups, mainly for project coordinators, that get coordination support

Funding:

- started without funding in 2014 with a lot of volunteer work by the two founders
- 2017 first external funding by the university through performance agreements with the ministry
- 2019 full funding for two senior scientists, a student co-worker and annual budget through the university
- made possible through change in rectorate that was very fond of citizen science
- no membership fees due to high workload with administration

Target group & communication:

- only institutions can be members
- communication mainly through e-mail, newsletter and mailing list
- no dedicated person for external communication; main channels are Facebook, LinkedIn and Youtube, monthly podcast or blog to communicate mainly with citizens and other people interested in cs
- press releases are only used when something newsworthy happened

Data:

- provision of templates for DMPs
- organization of webinars on open data
- no project research data are collected or stored on Österreich forscht
- no database per se on metadata about projects listed on Österreich forscht

iedereen
wetenschapper

Network/platform name:

Iedereenwetenschapper.be

Country: Belgium

Website:

<https://www.iedereenwetenschapper.be/>

Coordination by: Eos Wetenschap vzw

Contact person: Liesbeth Gijsel

E-Mail: liesbeth.gijsel@eos.be

Active since: 2015

Aims:

- Communication to the broad public: Iedereen Wetenschapper is a platform that shows CS projects that seek participants. People that are interested, can browse around to search projects they like. (additional communication via newsletter, social media and channels of our company Eos Wetenschap)
- Support for project leaders: publication and promotion of their projects
- Collaboration with CS community: partnership with Scivil (CS network Flanders), first steps to collaboration with new CS network in the Netherlands, partnerships in CS projects (eg Big Sea Shell Count)

Setup: na

Activities:

- Monthly newsletter
- Communication via Instagram, Facebook, Eos Wetenschap
- Annual: Big Sea Shell Count (as partner)
- Media Partner for citizen science projects

Funding:

- Part of Eos Wetenschap, non-profit organization for science journalism, that is partly funded by the Flemish Government (science communication).

Target group & communication:

- The broad public: everyone who might be interested in participating in a citizen science project

Data: na

Scivil

Citizen Science
Vlaanderen

Network/platform name: Scivil

Country: Belgium

Website: <https://www.scivil.be/>

Coordination by: Scivil (Roger Van Overstraeten Society vzw)

Contact person: Annelies Duerinckx

E-Mail: annelies@scivil.be

Active since: 2019

Aims:

- Promoting citizen science to potential citizen science stakeholders (e.g. academia, local and regional policy makers, civil society organisations, ...)
- Creating networking opportunities for citizen science stakeholders and establishing a strong CS community (together with partners such as the Flemish platform Iedereen Wetenschapper)
- Supporting citizen science initiatives with tailored advice, the creation of guides&toolkits, workshops and lectures
- Innovating/experimenting with citizen science through project partnerships.

Setup:

- funded by the Flemish government in Belgium
- added as an extension to science communication organisation 'RVO-society'

Activities:

- Bi-annual networking day and seminar/conference
- Monthly newsletter
- Coaching of CSIs
- Lectures and workshops on CS
- Creation of thematic CS Guides
- Mapping the Belgian CS landscape
- Working groups on specific CS themes and topics

Funding:

- The Flemish Government

Target group & communication:

- CS practitioners and central actors at research oriented organisations supporting CSI's in their organisation

Data: na

CITIZEN SCIENCE

Občanská věda v České republice

Network/platform name: Citizen Science CZ

Country: Czech Republic

Website: <http://www.citizenscience.cz/>

Coordination by: Czech Academy of Sciences
(Institute of Geonics)

& Tomas Bata University

Contact person: Jakub Trojan, Eva Nováková

E-Mail: trojan@utb.cz;

eva.novakova@ugn.cas.cz

Active since: 2019

Aims:

- Promoting citizen science (to communities, authorities, local stakeholders, etc...)
- Support for project leaders: publication and promotion of their projects
- Creating database of existing projects/available opportunities

Setup: na

Activities:

- Nothing regular
- Promotion of current campaigns of individual projects or inter/national events via social networks

Funding:

- started as part of project – programming the platform was funded.
- since the end of the project is all work voluntary or partly funded from slightly related projects

Target group & communication:

- founders of citizen science projects
- broad public interested in CS projects

Data:

- no data is stored on the platform. The the platform serves as a database of existing projects that can be solved in the Czech environment and links to websites/contact persons managing individual projects

Network/platform name: Citizen Science Italia

Country: Italy

Website: <https://www.citizenscience.it>

Coordination by: Citizen Science Italia ETS

Contact person: Andrea Sforzi

E-Mail: direzione@museonaturalemaremma.it

Active since: 2023

Aims:

- Networking: connecting project coordinators, citizens and practitioners—Development of citizen science: in working groups, at workshops etc. Public outreach: dedicated events or (co)organizing other events, social media.— Support and strengthen the Italian citizen science community
- Raise awareness of the importance of Citizen Science among various stakeholders
- Establish strategic partnerships with the Italian Ministry of Research and University and with the National Biodiversity Future Center (nbfc.it) to foster CS in the country and set up the national citizen science platform

Setup:

- Founded by an informal group of people already working in the CS field and/or interested in the topic. In the framework of a national conference held in 2021, the informal assembly made up by more than 100 participants decided to establish an association and set the basis for the following steps to be put in practice. The main output of this collaborative strength was a draft that a group of 10 founders further put forward to develop the formal documents needed to reach this goal. The 17th February 2023 the association Citizen Science Italia ETS was formally established and registered under the Italian law.

Activities:

- both hybrid and in person
- bi-annual national conference
- three Working Groups at the moment: Education, Young People, Health
- a citizen science day organised bi-annually, in connection with the conference
- collaboration and networking with institutions
- training courses on citizen science

Funding: na

Target group & communication: na

Data: na

Network/platform name: Citizen Science Nederland
Country: Netherlands
Website: www.citizenscience.nl
Coordination by: Co-coordination by Leiden University (Margaret & Anouk at the Citizen Science Lab) and Twente University (Maya & Sumeyye at Designlab).
Contact person: Anouk Spelt
E-Mail: info@citizenscience.nl/
Anouk@citizenscience.nl
Active since: Soft launch May 2022, Official launch May 2024

Aims:

- Providing researchers with guidance
- Connecting initiatives and actors
- Stimulating innovation (in particular connecting science and society)
- Strengthening connections
- Offering opportunities for new connections in the form of symposia, working groups, research into citizen science, and pilot projects (from science and society).
- Facilitating the formation of new consortia and the co-development of project concepts for key work such as Knowledge Infrastructures for CS (including funding applications)
- Lobbying national policy-makers and research-funders for needed funding, support and other 'enabling factors' for the whole field of practice

Setup:

- Soft launch in May 2022
- Low budget operation with team of 2 people from May 2022 – May 2024
- Team of 4 people (Network coordinator, Community Manager, Communications Manager and CS Hubs coordinator) from May 2024 for 4 years

Activities:

- Knowledge Platform (www.citizenscience.nl)
- Communityhub (JOGL)
- Annual network meeting
- Monthly newsletter and social media channels
- Currently 5 working and thematic groups
- National Citizen Science Expo (bi-annually)
- Series of webinars, workshops and meetings (not yet started)

Funding:

- Initial funding from Dutch Research Council for 1 year in 2022 to soft launch the network.
- Follow-up funding from Open Science NL, part of the Dutch Research Council in May 2024 for 4 years (total amount €1.1 million).

Target group & communication:

- Citizen Science practitioners from across the quadruple helix
- Broad public interested in Citizen Science.

Data:

- Nothing at the moment but we would like to provide resources about data ethics, data storage, data management plans.
- We will not store data from CS projects ourselves but will sign post to data platforms

Network/platform name: Rede Portuguesa de Ciência Cidadã/RPCC

Country: Portugal

Website: <https://www.cienciacidada.pt/>

Coordination by: Rede Portuguesa de Ciência Cidadã

Contact person: Cristina Luís

E-Mail: cmluis@fc.ul.pt

Active since: 2019

Aims:

- Promote greater knowledge of what citizen science is and greater engagement of society in science through this practice
- Support and strengthen the Portuguese citizen science community
- Raise awareness of the importance of Citizen Science among various stakeholders
- Establish strategic partnerships

Setup:

- Registered on November 2023
- With elected board from April 2024

Activities:

- Biennial meetings since 2017
- Major working groups:
 - Education and learning
 - Societal engagement and inclusivity
 - Engagement with local communities and authorities
 - International networks and projects

Funding:

- No stable funding; gets funding for specific activities such as the biennial meetings

Target group & communication:

- Platform connected with EU-Citizen science; social media activity (instagram, LinkedIn)

Data:

Network/platform name: Schweiz Forscht

Country: Switzerland

Website: <https://www.schweizforscht.ch>

Coordination by: Science et Cité

Contact person: Tiina Staempfli

E-Mail: tiina.staempfli@science-et-cite.ch

Active since: 2015

Aims:

- We inform, sensitise and communicate about citizen science
- Networking and foster mutual learning
- We observe, anticipate and set topics

Setup:

- founded by Science et Cité after a survey amongst CS Stakeholders in 2014
- Projectphase 2015–19
- Programm Citizen Science with Mandat by Swiss Academies of Arts and Sciences 2020-
- Advisory Board 2023-
- Swiss Expert Group on Citizen Science (2022–24): Citizen Science in Switzerland: Taking Stock and Ways into the Future. SUGGESTED CITATION
- Swiss Expert Group for Citizen Science (2024). Citizen Science in Switzerland: Taking Stock and Ways into
- the Future. Swiss Academies Report: 19 (5)

Activities:

- foster mutual learning and strengthen CS in CH:
- Host of 1st national meeting for CS stakeholders in 2020 with the result co-created 10 Swiss CS Principles
- Networkmeetings (2–4 p.a.),

- national and local outreach (depending on the activity)
 - both hybrid and in person (depending on the activity)
 - for project coordinators, citizens, researchers, funders (depending on the activity)
 - aims are networking, development of citizen science, public outreach (depending on the activity)
 - some working groups
 - more activities in French and Italian speaking part of CH in development.
- Organizer and Host of ECSA 2018 in Geneva as well as CitSciHelvetia23, the Swiss citizen Science Conference in Solothurn (2023)

Funding:

- Fundraising for project Schweiz forscht (2015–2017)
- Fundraising (2018–20)
- funding in federal multiyear plan for education, research and innovation:
- Multiyear plan by Swiss Academies (2021–24)
- Multiyear plan by Swiss Academies (2025–28)
- <https://akademien-schweiz.ch/en/uber-uns/mandat/mehrjahresplanung-2025-2028/>

Target group & communication:

- communication via social media (linkedin group schweiz forscht, linkedin Science et Cité, bluesky and instagramm Science et Cité), emails, newsletter
- dedicated person for external communication in Citizen Science Team and dedicated person for corporate communication Science et Cité
- communication in German and French, some also in English depending on content. Very few also in Italian (Swiss Principles).

Data:

- organization of webinars on open data (DACH AG)

Network/platform name: citizenscience.eu

Country: Europe

Website: citizenscience.eu

Coordination by: ECSA

Contact person: Carolina Doran and Dorte Riemenschneider

E-Mail: carolina.doran@ecsa.ngo,
d.riemenschneider@ecsa.ngo

Active since: 2019

Aims:

- citizenscience.eu is the European reference point for CS, supporting knowledge sharing across networks and audiences, from participants and practitioners to researchers and policymakers.
- The platform offers access to projects, resources, events, and tools related to CS.
- A key feature is the ECS Academy, providing self-paced courses, teaching materials, and optional instructor-led trainings tailored to specific needs.

Setup:

- Developed in the EU-Citizen.Science project (Horizon 2020, 2018–2021) to create a European knowledge and learning platform for citizen science. Further development through the ECS project (Horizon Europe, 2022–2026). Hosted and managed by ECSA.

Activities:

- Clustering events across Europe
- Capacity building and thematic trainings
- Showcasing citizen science projects and best practices
- Providing access to tools, guidelines, and methods
- Promoting cross-border collaboration and community building
- Key service: The ECS Academy, the central hub for citizen science training in Europe, offering structured learning, curated courses, and educational resources.

Funding:

- Initially funded under Horizon 2020 (EU-Citizen.Science). Further development funded by Horizon Europe (ECS project 2022–2026). Maintenance supported through ECSA.

Target group & communication:

- Citizen science practitioners, researchers, policymakers, educators, civil society, and the public. Communicated through ECS platform, newsletters, webinars, social media, and events.

Data:

- Does not collect primary data. Functions as a meta-platform linking to projects, tools, and data sources. Promotes FAIR principles and ethical standards.

Network/platform name: The European Citizen Science Association (ECSA)

Country: Europe

Website: <https://www.ecsa.ngo/>

Coordination by: ECSA

Contact person: Dorte Riemenschneider

E-Mail: d.riemenschneider@ecsa.ngo

Active since: 2014

Aims:

- ECSA aims to advance citizen science as a credible, inclusive, and impactful approach to research, education, and policy. It supports the community by providing frameworks, building capacity, fostering collaboration, and promoting citizen engagement in science across Europe.

Setup:

- Non-profit membership association founded in 2013. Legally based in Germany. Brings together members and partners from Europe and beyond.

Activities:

- Coordinates EU projects, runs citizenscience.eu, hosts thematic working groups, develops frameworks (e.g. 10 Principles), and facilitates networking, events, and policy dialogue across Europe.

Funding:

- Funded through EU projects (e.g. Horizon, Erasmus+), other grants, membership fees, and in-kind contributions from institutional partners.

Target group & communication:

- Target groups include researchers, practitioners, civil society, educators, policymakers, and the public. Communication through events, website, ECS platform, newsletter, social media, and publications.

Data:

- Does not collect primary data. Promotes FAIR principles, ethical standards, and good practices in citizen science data management.

Network/platform name: Virtual Ecosystem for Research Activation – VERA

Country: Europe

Website: <https://vera.operas-eu.org/>

Coordination by: OPERAS

Contact person: Alessia Smaniotto

E-Mail: alessia.smaniotto@openedition.org

Active since: 2023

Aims:

- Enable the growth of citizen science projects in the social sciences and humanities by promoting CS within the SSH and viceversa; facilitate matchmaking between engaged stakeholders and SSH researchers, provide an online space to manage their project and find funding; provide trainings and facilitate mutual learning opportunities on participatory research with the SSH; give visibility to CS initiatives within the SSH

Setup:

- Funded by an EU project 2021–2023

Activities:

- Funded by an EU project 2021–2023
Trainings on SSH CS; advocacy activities for SSH CS; partnership buildings with funders; building projects opportunities to improve the platform with CS networks or services

Funding:

- Basic running maintenance: OPERAS RI; further development: projects' funds based

Target group & communication:

- Researchers and practitioners willing to engage in CS projects including the SSH disciplines

Data:

- Does not collect primary data

